

Speculation on Photon Spin and Spatial Invariance

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In a previous note (1), we argued that the expression E (electric field) = $-\text{grad } \phi - \partial A/\partial t$ arises because E , a measurable, must depend on the measurable vector $(x-vt, y, z)$ for a moving point charge. If one considers a rest frame for the point charge, then $E'' = -\text{grad}'' \phi''$, and Lorentz transforms $(0, \phi'') \rightarrow (A, \phi)$, where $\phi = g \phi''(x'', y'', z'')$ with $g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ then $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ leads to a vector of: $\{ g g(x-vt), y, z \}$. This is not the measurable vector and so E cannot simply be $-\text{grad } \phi$. $\partial A/\partial t$ needs to be added to convert $g g(x-vt) \rightarrow (x-vt)$.

Here, we argue that this criterion is linked to invariance (isotropy) of space. The expression $x-vt$ is due to motion, but does not upset a sense of invariance throughout space, but $g g(x-vt)$ does. $g g$ implies that space in the x direction is weighted whereas it is not in the y and z directions. The addition of $\partial A/\partial t$ to E removes this bias and creates invariance (isotropy). If such is the case, it seems that the consideration of three dimensions is essential, even though motion only occurs in one dimension, say the x .

In (1), we argued that given the form, $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \partial A/\partial t$, one may find solutions, $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \phi(1, 0, 0)$ ((1)) which yield $E(x \text{ direction}) = 0$. The solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ singles out the direction of motion and associates with it a quantity k . This is linked to w through: $\Delta(-\omega t + kx) = 0$ or $\Delta x / \Delta t = w/k = \text{speed}$. The solution ((1)) is problematic, however, for two reasons. First, $E=B=0$ which means the solution does not correspond to a physical observable, and secondly, it only acknowledges one dimension in space, x , both through $A = \phi(1, 0, 0)$ and $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$.

We argue that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \partial A/\partial t$ is based on invariance in 3-space and so all three dimensions need to be acknowledged. It is fine to consider $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ which treats x in a preferential manner and associates it with k , because there is preference, namely motion in the x direction and not in the y or z directions. Nevertheless, the two dimensions (z, y) must also be manifest. Two ways to do this are:

$\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, $A = \phi(1, 1, 1)$ or $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$, $A = \phi(1, 1, 0)$ or $A = \phi(1, 0, 1)$. The problem with the latter is that it treats E and B differently (different magnitudes, while the $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ solution is associated with no charge or source and implies E and B should have the same magnitude.

Thus, one has E and B perpendicular to each other and lying in a plane perpendicular to motion. There is motion associated with momentum k in the x direction due to invariance, but there is also invariance in the plane perpendicular to motion, because there need not be fixed E and B positions, rather these may rotate through $-\omega t + kx$. Thus, invariance leads to motion in both the x direction (associated with linear momentum) and in the plane perpendicular to x associated with rotational momentum or spin. This spin is part of the overall field energy: $\int \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \int \frac{1}{\mu_0} B \cdot B$, just like the momentum k , where $w = kc$, is linked with total energy as well.

Invariance and Motion

It seems that the notion of invariance is linked with motion in the following sense. If one dimensional space is invariant, then each x point is the same as the other. There exists the same probability for a point to be at x_1 as it to be at x_1+dx , where dx is small. Physically, however, one must move the object from x_1 to x_1+dx . If the object moves at constant velocity, it samples different x values, one after the other, spending the same time in each dx . Thus, invariance in one direction is linked with linear momentum.

If a rod is fixed at one end in a plane and there is invariance in the plane, it has the same probability to lie at any angle provided that the fixed end point does not change. This gives rise to the notion of constant angular momentum. A constant angular velocity ensures each angle is given the same time weight.

$E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial As a Statement of Invariance

In a rest frame, a point charge obeys: $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, where

$$\phi = q/(4\pi\epsilon_0) \cdot 1/\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2} \quad ((1))$$

In the moving frame, $(t, \phi) \rightarrow$ Lorentz transforms $\rightarrow (A, \phi)$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \phi &= g \phi(x', y', z') \text{ and} \\ A &= v e(x) g \phi(1, 0, 0) \text{ with } g = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \text{ and} \\ x' &= g(x-vt), y' = y, z' = z. \end{aligned}$$

If one argues that $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame, then the vector portion is:

$$\{ g g(x-vt), y, z \} \quad ((2))$$

In (1), we argued that ((2)) is not allowable because E is a physical measurable and one does not measure $g g(x-vt)$, but rather $x-vt$. An extra piece, dA/dt partial, is needed to remove $g g$.

Here, we argue that this statement is equivalent to arguing that 3-space is invariant (isotropic). $x-vt$ refers to motion and does not break 3-space invariance, but $g g$ does because it weights one dimension (x) in a different way than the two others. $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ ensures spatial invariance in three dimensions, even though motion is in one dimension. We argue that this means that:

$$\text{3-space must be acknowledged even for one dimensional motion.} \quad ((3))$$

Given $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, one may have a math solution: $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \phi(1, 0, 0)$, such that $E(x) = 0$. It is fine that $E(x)$ is 0, because there is already a variable k associated with x motion which may have a physical meaning. The problem with the above

solution is that $E=B=0$. This means that there is no energy density associated with this solution, where:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((4))$$

A further problem, however, is that the solution does not acknowledge the y, z directions which violates ((3)). All three spatial dimensions must be acknowledged, we argue.

This leads to other solutions:

- (A) $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \phi(1,1,1)$ and
- (B) $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \phi(1,1,0)$ or $A = \phi(1,0,1)$

The problem with (B) is that it does not yield E magnitude = B magnitude.

The x direction is singled out via $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ with the parameter k possibly representing a physical entity while $B(x)=E(x)=0$, .i.e. there is no E or B field x component. E and B fields are perpendicular to each other and the x direction.

Spatial Invariance and Motion (Momentum)

In the above section, we noted that all three spatial dimensions must be acknowledged. The x is acknowledged through k and the y-z plane by the vectors E, B . It may be shown that:

$$\int dv \frac{1}{\mu_0} E \times B / \int dv = k = \int \text{Poynting momentum density} / \int dv \quad ((5))$$

k is a physical momentum value associated with invariance in the x direction, .i.e. each x point has the same time weight for constant motion.

We argue that the same kind of invariance exists in the z-y plane. There is no reason to have E or B in a fixed position, they just need to be perpendicular. For circular polarization: $E = (0, \cos(-\omega t + kx), \sin(-\omega t + kx))$ and $B = (0, -\sin(\omega t + kx), \cos(-\omega t + kx))$ one has constant magnitude but rotating E and B fields.

There is rotational motion or angular momentum due to invariance in the z-y plane. This is called spin, but overall it contributes to the energy density:

$$\text{Energy density} = .5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B \quad ((6))$$

This spin, however, is coupled to linear momentum (x direction motion) through $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ and $\sin(-\omega t + kx)$ and $w=kc$. Thus, spin might be overlooked because it is incorporated in energy w and (k, w) transform as a 4-vector, nevertheless it is physically present, represents physical angular momentum for circular polarization and is linked, we argue, to invariance. Given that $w=kc$, one might argue that linear momentum here is also incorporated into energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ so that the vector associated with E for a point charge in an moving frame is: $\{ x-vt, y, z \}$ and not $\{ \gamma(x-vt), y, z \}$ which arises if one only considers $-\text{grad } \phi$. We argue this implies that three-space is isotropic, i.e. x, y, z carry the same weight. Even though one has one dimensional motion, all three dimensions of space must be considered, we suggest.

We note that the form of E allows for the solution: $\phi = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ and $A = \phi(1, 1, 1)$. Here the x direction is singled out by k , but there exists E and B fields perpendicular to each other and of equal magnitude in the z - y plane. Thus, the z and y directions are acknowledged. One may show that $k = \int dv \frac{1}{\mu_0} \text{ExB} / \int dv / \int dv$, so k is linear momentum due to spatial invariance.

There also exists rotational invariance in the z - y plane and so this should be associated with angular momentum, called spin. This is linked to circular polarization: $E = (0, \cos(-\omega t + kx), \sin(-\omega t + kx))$ and $B = (0, -\sin(\omega t + kx), \cos(-\omega t + kx))$ and contributes to the energy density: $\epsilon_0 \cdot 5 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ and so spin is sometimes overlooked.

Thus, $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ suggests that all three dimensions of space be considered and invariance in x leads to linear momentum k while invariance in the z - y plane, to angular momentum or spin. Both k , through $\omega = kc$ and spin, through energy density represent the same energy. It is just that this energy is being manifest through two different kinds of momenta which are coupled because $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ contains k .

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on the Photon Solution from Maxwell's EM Equations Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)